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Improving NDIS access

*Improving Communications with
Aboriginal people with hearing loss*

RECOMENDATION OF THE 2017 AMA INDIGENOUS HEALTH REPORT CARD

“A national approach to developing hearing loss-responsive communication strategies in all government and non-government agencies providing services to Indigenous people including - but not limited to - health, mental health, justice, and employment services.”

Structure

This presentation has three parts

1. It explains why Aboriginal experience so much more hearing loss
2. It shows how to identify who has a hearing loss and
3. It talks about how to mitigate the communication disadvantages related to hearing loss.

Conductive Hearing Loss

➤ Sound is conducted through the outer and middle ear.

➤ Most often caused by middle ear infections.

➤ Often temporary but if damage to middle ear structures through repeated infections can be permanent.

➤ The massive level of hearing loss among Indigenous people is because of this kind of ear infection driven conductive hearing loss.

A DISEASE OF DISADVANTAGE

Most common reason children visit doctors

But some experience it earlier, longer more often

The socially and economically disadvantaged

- Crowded housing
- Poor nutrition
- Poor access to medical treatment
- Possible anatomical predispositions

We all live in this house

HOW MANY CHILDREN HAVE IT?

One third of the children in
EARLY CHILDHOOD CLASSES
have an unidentified CHL

Between 40-90% of
**INDIGENOUS AND PACIFIC
CHILDREN** have an
unidentified CHL at any
point in time

HOW MANY INDIGENOUS ADULTS HAVE IT?

Up to 50% of Indigenous adults in remote communities have some degree of hearing loss

In some specific populations it is higher

- ✓ 94% of prison inmates
- ✓ Higher among lower achieving students
- ✓ Higher among people who are not working
- ✓ Higher among homeless
- ✓ Higher among those living in crowded housing

AUDITORY PROCESSING PROBLEMS

➤ A history of **OTITIS MEDIA** can lead to auditory processing difficulties

➤ Children and adults with auditory processing problems have **DIFFICULTIES UNDERSTANDING** speech especially when it is noisy

➤ **'TEMPORARY' HEARING LOSS** may lead to permanent auditory processing problems

HOW MANY CHILDREN HAVE IT?

About 7-10% of children in the
GENERAL POPULATION have
Auditory Processing Disorder

One study found 40% of **INDIGENOUS PEOPLE** have signs of auditory processing problems.

LONG TERM IMPACTS OF EARLY ONSET HEARING LOSS

Childhood
Conductive
Hearing Loss

Schooling
EMPLOYMENT
Health
SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL WELLBEING
Criminal justice

SCHOOLING

- Children with hearing loss treated as having **BEHAVIOUR** problems
- **DIFFICULTIES** learning
- Poorer **ATTENDANCE**
- Lower **ACHIEVEMENT**

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rekk0tpWQyU>

EMPLOYMENT

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uyzsfPbXlr8>

➤ More UNEMPLOYMENT

➤ TRAINING challenges

➤ COMMUNICATION difficulties

➤ Lower INCOME

➤ Difficulties with CHANGE

For more information on this watch:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Aj20fGQMwYo>

HEALTH

Adult hearing loss is associated with a greater risk of:

- DIABETES
- Elevated **BLOOD PRESSURE**
- HEART ATTACK
- **HIGHER SICKNESS** impact profiles

Hearing loss **LIMITS ACCESS** to health services and communication and treatment outcomes when accessed.

SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL WELLBEING

➤ Those with hearing loss experience more **FRUSTRATION, STRESS, SOCIAL EXCLUSION**

➤ Coping strategies **FOSTER ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION** – anticipation and comparison

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zD_iifnzaeo&t=5s

CRIMINAL JUSTICE

- More often **ARRESTED, CONVICTED AND IMPRISONED**
- Difficulties with **COMMUNICATION** with police, in court, in prison
- Prison further **ISOLATES**

94% of Indigenous inmates in The NT found to have a **significant Hearing Loss** (21 decibels in better ear)

SENSORINUERAL HEARING LOSS

- Sound is transmitted through **ELECTRO CHEMICAL MEANS** through the inner ear.
- Hearing loss caused by damage to the **COCHLEA**.
- Damage results in **PERMANENT** hearing loss.
- Can be mild to moderate – hard of hearing – often caused by **EXCESSIVE NOISE EXPOSURE**.
- Or severe to profound where people have difficulty with **VERBAL COMMUNICATION** at all.
- This is **DEAF** community.

Deaf Mob and the NDIS Darwin

Story Telling... Learning Map

Yarning circle – narrative and body languages

- Narrative
- Body language
- Facial expressions
- Hand talk
- Eye movement
- Cultural boundaries
- LORE

Engaging Deaf Mob and their children and families.

- Walking in four worlds
- Taking time to understand processes
- Respecting space
- Effective communication strategies

Advocacy

- Listening to Deaf mob
- Providing information appropriately
- Using services – interpreters
- Understanding communication styles
- Independent needs
- Family needs
- Cultural needs

Auslan in Deaf mob context

- Data
- Educational
- Social
- Medical
- Legal
- Families
- Code switching

IDENTIFICATION OF HEARING LOSS AND AUDITORY PROCESSING PROBLEMS

Some Screening Tools

INDICATORS OF HEARING LOSS AT HOME

- › Does **NOT TALK** much
- › Uses **ACTIONS** or **POINT** more
- › Takes longer to **TELL** things
- › Needs people to **CALL OUT LOUD** to get their attention
- › Likes to do things their **OWN WAY**
- › **SITS CLOSE** to music or TV
- › Often hard to **UNDERSTAND**

INDICATORS OF HEARING LOSS AT SCHOOL

- DISRUPTIVE in in class
- Often need INDIVIDUAL help
- Does NOT ANSWER questions
- Make few CONTRIBUTIONS to class conversations
- Has difficulty FOLLOWING TEACHER directions
- ACHIEVING at a lower level especially in UPPER PRIMARY CLASSES

INDICATIONS OF HEARING LOSS AMONG ADULTS FACE TO FACE

INDICATOR	RELATION TO HEARING LOSS
Says little	Wary of being shamed by misunderstanding.
Misunderstands comments or questions	Often misunderstands key word and has difficulty understanding, or goes on a wrong conversational tangent.
Long response times to questions	Taking longer to respond, compared with others from the same community, is common because more time is needed to understand what is said and construct a reply.
Speaks quietly, or loudly	It is difficult for people with hearing problems to judge the right level to speak at in different environments.

INDICATIONS (CONTINUED)

INDICATOR	RELATION TO HEARING LOSS
Intense face-watching	Face-watching and lip-reading to better understand what is said.
Displays signs of listening overload	Listening is harder work for those with listening problems. They may have to think intensely when listening and tire quickly. If long conversation they may develop a blank gaze and become minimally responsive.
Have difficulties in expressing what they want to say	The impact of listening problems on expressive language development can result in people experiencing difficulties in constructing what they want to say. This is especially so if they are put on the spot. They may prefer and need to prepare responses.

INDICATIONS (CONTINUED)

INDICATOR	RELATION TO HEARING LOSS
Scripted monologues	People sometimes cope with problems with verbal expression by developing a mental 'script' for what they want to say. They may follow this script and deliver a 'monologue' and ignore, or become discomfited by, interruptions.
Bring someone to help with communication	Relies on others to help with communication.
Long response times to questions	Taking longer to respond, compared with others from the same community, is common because more time is needed to understand what is said and construct a reply.
Speaks quietly, or loudly	It is difficult for people with hearing problems to judge the right level to speak at in different environments.

TOOLS FOR SCREENING FOR HEARING LOSS

BLIND MANS SIMON SAYS

- Need one person with known **GOOD HEARING**
- **OBJECTIVE** test

PHOENIX LISTENING SURVEY

- Self report – person has reason to **MINIMIZE** or **DENY PROBLEM** may distort results

PHOENIX ADULT LISTENING SURVEY PART I

QUESTION 1

You are talking with someone and there is a TV on in the same room. Without turning the TV down, can you follow what the other person is saying?

5	4	3	2	1
Very Easy	Easy	Little bit hard	Hard	Very hard

Please ✓

QUESTION 2

You are talking with someone in a quiet room. Can you follow what they are saying?

5	4	3	2	1
Very Easy	Easy	Little bit hard	Hard	Very hard

Please ✓

ACTION AREAS TO IMPROVE COMMUNICATION

BEING NON JUDGMENTAL

“You see that look, the look that tells you they are thinking you are some stupid blackfella and you don’t want to say you don’t understand; ‘Can you tell me it again?’”

“You just want to get away and never want to work with them again if you can help it.”

NON JUDGMENTAL
adults

People with hearing loss regularly experience **BEING JUDGED** for their difficulties in understanding what others say or expressing what they want to say. They are highly attuned to **VISUAL INDICATORS** of ‘judgement’

	EASY LISTENING	HARD LISTENING
PLACE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Quiet → People talking loud enough 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Noisy → People talk quietly
PERSON	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Know person well → Does not judge when don't understand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Person who is not well known → Often judgmental when don't understand
MESSAGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Know words being spoken → Show as well as talk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Don't know words → Just talk no showing

THOSE WITH HEARING LOSS

*I thought they were
just more cultural*

➤ LESS LIKELY to speak English well

➤ UNDERSTAND BETTER in their most familiar language

➤ EXHIBIT MORE responses that are seen as derived from culture

- ✓ Often take longer to respond
- ✓ More reliant on visual aspects of communication
- ✓ Understand better when communication within familiar cultural processes.

➤ BUT

➤ May MAKE MORE EYE CONTACT because they need to face watch

AVOIDANCE AS RESPONSE TO ANXIETY MAGNIFIES COMMUNICATION PROBLEMS

What starts in difficulties
hearing what is said,
ends up in also having
difficulties understanding
what is heard

Minimize avoidance

By lessening likelihood of shame and worry.

Make what is unknown familiar.

- Use pre-learning.
- Enable communication support from known people.
- Use familiar language.
- In good acoustic environment.
- Avoid negative judgement

STRENGTH FOCUSED APPROACH

- Focus on persons strengths in **DISCUSSING NEEDS**
- Find out about strengths **FROM FAMILY**
- Incorporate strengths in discussion about **SUPPORT NEEDS**
- In conversation weave discussion of strengths into **IDENTIFICATION OF SUPPORT NEEDS**, so process does not demoralize.

INTERACTION OF HEARING LOSS WITH OTHER DISABILITIES

HEARING LOSS PROBLEMS MAY

CO EXIST WITH AND CONTRIBUTE TO SYMPTOMS of ADHD, dyslexia, ASD, anxiety problems, antisocial behaviour, and other learning problems

May be MISTAKENLY BE DIAGNOSED as ADHD, ASD.

HEARING LOSS STRUCTURES **NEGATIVE** EXPERIENCES

EXPERIENCE MORE STRESS

- People with hearing loss experience **MORE STRESS**
- **HARDER WORK** to understand
 - ↳ **MISCOMMUNICATION** and **LISTENING** overload
- **DANGEROUS** living in 'auditory' world
 - ↳ Dogs, cars, human predators

**OFTEN EXCLUDED,
ISOLATED AND POORLY
INFORMED**

» **COMMUNICATION PROBLEMS** mean
people often

- ✓ Feel excluded
- ✓ Miss out on information
- ✓ Feel alone even with others

*“Hearing loss contributes to intense ‘jealousing’. That kind of jealousing, when it’s extreme, includes a kind of **a scanning for signs and subtle indicators of infidelity**... this is a situation where misperceptions and misinterpretations are really likely.. wariness and watchfulness result in morbid jealousy or preoccupations about **black magic**... interpersonal problems and social issues really come to the fore. Substance use on top of that can amplify the difficulties and precipitate frank psychotic features.”*

- Ernest Hunter, psychiatrist

JEALOUSING AND BLACK MAGIC

WHEN HEARING LOSS IS NOT IDENTIFIED IMPACTS ARE MAGNIFIED

CRITICISM,
JUDGEMENT
AND BLAME
FOR NOT
UNDERSTANDING

› Negative judgements by others or self more likely when hearing loss is not identified and/or its likely impacts are not known.

COMING TO THE CITY

Common pattern of people with multiple complex disabilities eventually being moved from a remote to an urban center to meet their support needs

- ✓ This involves **LOSS OF CONTACT** with family and culture
- ✓ And the people who they have established **COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES**
- ✓ **EXPECTATIONS** to learn more English, Auslan and to stop using their traditional sign language
- ✓ Not using traditional sign languages means **LOSS OF CONTACT** with family and culture
- ✓ This can escalate **PROBLEMATIC BEHAVIOURS**.

**MAINTAINING CONTACT WITH FAMILY, COUNTRY,
AND CULTURE ESSENTIAL**

Online Training

There is an online version of the training being developed.
Let people who may be interested know about it.
They can register interest by contacting
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